

Improving A Probabilistic Approach to Assessing Building Performance

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Abstract

Buildings and their associated electrical and mechanical systems are responsible for 35 percent of U.S. carbon emissions, and it is estimated that up to 30 percent of the energy used in commercial buildings is wasted due to inefficient operation and poorly performing control systems. Improving building operation typically involves an expert manually sifting through data from the control system to identify issues. We have previously proposed a novel standardized “control score” concept to simplify control performance assessment by quantifying three aspects of system control in terms of probabilities. This work focuses on improvements to these probability measures and presents an improved method for assessing control stability using a combination of the Hurst exponent and measures of the variance and periodicity in time series data. We also present a data-driven approach for assessing the supervisory aspect of control performance based on a multivariate analysis in a feature space determined via clustering. Results will be shown from application of these methods to over 70 buildings across three organizations.

Key Words: building control score, ControlScore, control performance assessment, supervisory control, building energy use, HVAC systems, control systems

1. Introduction

Building control systems are generating more data than ever, but pinpointing poorly performing systems requires expertise and a lot of time. Improvements to building control systems can lead to energy savings and increased occupant comfort. In an optimized system, process variables (PVs) such as air temperature will closely follow their desired setpoints (SPs) and avoid excess energy use. Typically, experts must manually inspect individual control loops to identify poor performance and opportunities for improvement. However, this approach is difficult in modern buildings that have a prohibitively large number of controllers. Therefore, the building industry would benefit from a single metric that could be tracked to evaluate and compare building control performance. ControlScore (Salsbury et al. 2023) provides a standard way to assess building control performance without the need for a controls expert sifting through data. In this work, we present improvements to the component scores that comprise the overall ControlScore for a given control loop.

2. ControlScore Calculation Method Overview

The ControlScore evaluates different aspects of the control hierarchy via quantification of the following three different aspects of control performance:

1. Proximity of process variable to setpoint
2. Stability and presence of oscillatory behavior in the process variable
3. Supervisory control assessment: comparison of the observed setpoint trajectory with references

Each of the component scores are derived from various probability distributions and then rescaled to a 0-10 value. The proximity aspect measures how closely the PV is being controlled by the SP

and compares the distribution of points in the PV to the distribution of points in the SP. Refer to the original ControlScore paper (Salsbury et al. 2023) for a description of that methodology. The stability component measures how the PV fluctuates around the SP over time with the intent to identify and separate controller “hunting” from stable controller performance. The supervisory control assessment of the SP trajectory measures how closely the actual SP resembles an expected, or desired, reference trajectory. This paper focuses on improving the calculation methodology for the stability and supervisory assessments.

3. ControlScore Methodology Improvements

3.1 Stability Assessment Improvements

The original method proposed for stability assessment in the ControlScore (Salsbury et al. 2023) looked for periodicity in the time-series data by evaluating the zero-crossing frequency (i.e., how often the sign of the error signal changes from positive to negative and vice versa) in the observed error signal. This “zero-crossing” method used a normalized statistic for the expected zero-crossing rate compared to the actual zero-value crossing rate in the error signal to calculate the probability of the error signal containing non-random dominant frequencies.

This method was applied to a real-world dataset of control system data from an enterprise building control system that integrates and centralizes building control data from over 70 buildings located throughout the conterminous United States. Examination of control loops within this dataset revealed that control loops would receive very different stability scores in sequential periods with no change in operation. An example of this is shown in Figure 1. It is unclear exactly why seemingly similar periods would receive such disparate scores. However, it is likely due to slight differences in the error signals’ zero-crossing rate. In Figure 1, the first period of data (received a score of 9.8) has two separate excursions from the deadband, while the second period (received a score of 0) has only one such excursion. This slight difference may be the cause of the score disparity.

Figure 1: Example of different stability scores for sequential periods. The first period (blue line) received a score of 9.8 while the next period (green line) received a score of 0.

Further exploration of the calculated stability scores in the real-world building control system data showed that the “zero-crossing” method essentially produced a binary stability score as shown in Figure 2. A binary score is undesirable as it only provides information on the extreme ends of the stability scale and does not provide meaningful comparison between degrees of stability (i.e., a slight instability in the system would be scored equal to a very unstable system). Further, a binary stability

score would have an inflated impact on the combined overall ControlScore, which is comprised of three aspects of control performance.

Figure 2: Distribution of stability scores: “zero-crossing” method

We investigated an alternative stability measure to address this issue. The stability measure proposed here, the “ratio of the variances” method, is based on the same premise underlying the Harris index that good control is characterized by a feedback controller that can reject disturbances so that the error signal only contains random noise. The stability assessment therefore analyzes the error signal and calculates a probability related to its randomness. In typical HVAC systems, however, even well-performing controllers will take some time to reject disturbances, and this will appear as autocorrelation in the error signal that will make the signal be less random. Because we do not want to penalize this normal behavior, we obtained samples from the control loops at a slow enough frequency that effectively filters out the faster controller response dynamics. This filtering via sampling then leaves only longer and more persistent sources of autocorrelation. This will include oscillatory behavior and even oscillations that have frequencies faster than the sampling frequency due to aliased versions of the original signal being preserved.

A useful statistic can distinguish stable and non-stable time series sequences was proposed in Cao and Rhinehart (1995). This simple statistic uses second moment information but provides a normalization technique based on an alternative calculation of the second moment. The two second moment statistics are:

- standard deviation of the error signal: $s_e = std(e)$
- standard deviation of the sequential error differences: $s_d = std(\nabla e)$

Cao and Rhinehart (1995) showed that the ratio of these statistics has an expected value of one when the signal has a constant mean and contains only noise. Their ratio, R , is given by:

$$R = \frac{2s_e^2}{s_d^2} \quad (1)$$

No theoretical density functions were derived for the proposed R statistic but for this work, we assumed R is lognormal with an unknown variance. We therefore followed a similar process as before to derive a probability, but with the caveat that the variance of the density function is a parameter. First, we converted the lognormal statistic to a normal statistic $R \rightarrow R_N \in N(0, \sigma_R)$:

$$R_N = \ln(2s_e^2) - \ln(s_d^2) \quad (2)$$

The probability that the R is equal to one (stable) and hence that R_N is equal to zero is:

$$P = 2P(z < -|R_N|) \quad (3)$$

P is obtained from the cumulative distribution function for the normal distribution with a specified σ_R value.

This “ratio of the variances” method produced a more useful distribution of scores in the same real-world dataset as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Distribution of stability scores: “ratio of the variances” method

The Hurst exponent (H) has been used for control performance assessment in various applications (Das et al., 2016; Khosroshahi et al., 2022; Srinivasan 2012; Yagci and Böling, 2022). We investigated using a similar approach to improve the stability assessment. The Hurst exponents were calculated from the differenced error signals in the real-world dataset. Most of the loops were classified as anti-persistent ($H < 0.5$), as shown in Figure 4, suggesting stability.

Figure 4: Hurst exponents of real-world dataset

Comparing these scores to the “ratio of the variance” scores revealed a weak correlation (Pearson correlation coefficient = -0.35), indicating the methods somewhat agree on their stability

assessment. Figure 5 shows the stability scores calculated on a real-world dataset using both the “ratio of the variance” and the Hurst exponent method.

Figure 5: Comparison of stability scoring methods

We investigated both the “ratio of the variances” and the Hurst exponent methods for assessing stability to address the real-world performance issues of the originally proposed “zero-crossing” method. While the Hurst exponent method produced results that seem promising for future use, more work is needed to validate the method. The “ratio of the variances” method produced a more actionable distribution of scores than the original “zero-crossing” method and is now the basis for stability assessment in the ControlScore framework.

3.2 Supervisory Assessment Improvements

Supervisory control assessment was originally proposed as a comparison between the actual SP and a reference trajectory. Features were extracted from the actual setpoint profiles and a reference setpoint profile. The supervisory score would then be calculated using a distance metric between the actual setpoint feature tuple and the reference setpoint feature tuple. As described in the original ControlScore paper (Salsbury et al. 2023), a library or small set of typical setpoint trajectories would need to be assembled to measure the actual setpoints against. Due to unavailable metadata from control system data and a lack of the required reference trajectory library, this approach was not feasible for a real-world dataset of control system data.

As an alternative, we adopted the data-driven approach based on a multivariate analysis in a feature space determined via clustering described in the original paper. Similar to the approach proposed in the original paper, we determined a 0-10 score of the SP using the distance between a loop’s feature couplet and a reference feature couplet. However, instead of using a reference profile to determine the feature couplet, we used the population of control loops of the same type. The advantage of this method is that we did not need to have a library of reference SPs for each type of loop being investigated. This attribute becomes particularly valuable for assessing control loops where an existing “standard” control strategy does not exist.

We calculated the first two statistical moments (mean and standard deviation) of each loop. Using these two moments, we described each setpoint trajectory with a feature couplet made up of the mean ($m_1 = \mu_1$) and standard deviation ($m_2 = \sigma$): $x_i = m_{1,i}, m_{2,i}$. The set of features is then (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N) . However, instead of defining the reference point from an external profile with ideal characteristics, we defined the reference profile as $x_0 = m_{1,0}, m_{2,0}$ as the center of the feature space cluster defined as:

$$x_0 = (m_{1,0}, m_{2,0}) = \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^n m_{1,i}, \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^n m_{2,i} \right) \quad (4)$$

Real-world control system data often contain erroneous setpoint trajectories that would disproportionately impact the centroid. Therefore, it is best to remove these outlier setpoint features prior to calculating the reference setpoint couplet, x_0 . Many outlier detection and removal methods exist. Here we use a clustering approach via the density-based spatial clustering of applications with noise (DBSCAN) clustering algorithm (Ester et al. 1996; Schubert et al. 2017). We normalize each of the feature dimensions by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance using the sci-kit learn python package (Pedregosa et al. 2012) before clustering. We then separate the outlier control loops from the main cluster. We then calculate the Euclidean distance between the center of this cluster and each loops' feature couplet and convert this distance to a probability-based score using the same method described in the original ControlScore paper (reproduced here). The Euclidean distance between the reference setpoint feature couplet and the each of the actual setpoint feature couplets is calculated as:

$$d_i(x_i, x_0) = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^K (m_{j,i} - m_{j,0})^2} \quad (5)$$

Figure 6 illustrates the feature space from a set of real-world building control system setpoints. The setpoint features identified as belonging to the main cluster of features are shown as green points with the outlier clusters shown in other colors. The centroid of this "good" cluster of setpoints (calculated via Equation 5) is shown in red.

Figure 6: Feature clusters from a real-world zone temperature setpoint control loop dataset

As in the original paper, we assume that the features follow a multivariate normal distribution with K degrees of freedom. As we are considering a two-dimension feature space, there are $K = 2$ degrees of freedom. Finally, this distance is converted to a probability-based score using the chi-squared cumulative distribution function:

$$P_i = P(d_i^2 = 0) \quad (6)$$

where P_i is obtained from the cumulative chi-squared distribution function.

This method produces a reasonable distribution of supervisory scores in a real-world building control system dataset as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Supervisory ControlScore Distribution Using Feature Distance

Additionally, a qualitative assessment of the supervisory scores calculated via this method shows promising results. Figure 8 provides examples of loops assessed to have low supervisory scores of <1 . Figure 9 similarly shows examples of loops assigned high supervisory scores of >9 .

Figure 8: Example of control loops with a low ControlScore (<1). Zone temperature setpoints should be between 68-78°F.

Figure 9: Example of control loops with a high ControlScore (>9). Zone temperature setpoints should be between 68-78°F.

4. Conclusion

This paper has presented two improvements in the ControlScore methodology. The improved stability assessment methodology based on the “ratio of the variances” produces a meaningful distribution in real-world building control data, leading to a better characterization of performance. Further improvement in the stability assessment may be possible by incorporating the Hurst exponent method.

Additionally, the clustering approach originally proposed was modified to assess the supervisory aspect of control in reference to peer control loops instead of a library of pre-defined reference trajectories. This method was able to identify improper setpoints in a real-world building without needing a built-up library of reference setpoints. The improved supervisory assessment of the ControlScore method can now be applied in practice where it was previously not possible given the lack of an exhaustive set of standard setpoints.

Both improvements make the ControlScore framework more actionable when applied to real-world control system data, making the tool even more valuable to practitioners assessing control performance.

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